

SOCIAL-PEDAGOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF FORMING THE EXPERIENCE OF INTERPERSONAL VALUE RELATIONSHIP IN STUDENTS

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Abstract. *In this article, teaching students to value interpersonal relationships is of social and pedagogical importance, these relationships, in addition to ensuring stability between people, allow students to develop mentally and spiritually, and accelerate their educational activities. thought about giving. The theoretical foundations of this problem are also analyzed. Socio-pedagogical directions of creating valuable interpersonal experience in students are shown. This article serves as a methodological resource for professors, researchers and teachers.*

Tayanch so'zlar: shaxslararo munosabatlar, qadriyatli munosabatlar, ijtimoiy-pedagogik xususiyatlari, dialog, o'quvchilar, axborot almashish, muloqotga kirishish, munosabat o'rnatish.

Keywords: *interpersonal relations, value relations, socio-pedagogical features, dialogue, students, information exchange, communication, relationship building.*

The formation of interpersonal relationships among students has attracted the attention of many experts. This problem has not lost its relevance for many centuries. Humanity has always felt the need for interpersonal relationships. The change of generations requires that they assimilate the social experience of their ancestors. Interpersonal relationships are also an important part of the social experience that people need to learn. Various aspects of interpersonal relations are addressed in the sources of pedagogy, psychology and sociology devoted to the problem of interpersonal relations. In these sources, interpersonal relations are equated with the concepts of relations between people, joint activity, cooperation, dialogic relations, interpersonal communication, interpersonal communication. These views were studied from different angles in the works of R.Safarova, N.Dilova, F.Aminova, Z.Kholmatova, F.Muzaffarova, M.A'zamova, G.Akramova, B.Sa'dullaev.

According to T.A.Repina, interpersonal relations were manifested in the process of communication and mutual relations. It is interpersonal relationships that equate joint activities, attitudes, and interactions between people. A.F.Lazursky first addressed the issue of relationship. In the concept of personality, the issue of a person's reaction to external influences and stimuli at various levels is studied.

V.N.Myasishev devoted his psychological research to interpersonal relations. He managed to reveal the psychological connection of a person with surrounding things and people within the framework of the concept of relationship. Interpersonal relationships include relationships with objects and events in the external world. This includes, first of all, subject-object relations, that is, a person's relation to all objects. Also, the attitude towards other people is a component of interpersonal relations. Such relations can include subject-subject relations and interpersonal relations. For example, relationships between teachers and students, relationships between parents, and relationships between teammates. A person's attitude towards himself is also an integral part of interpersonal relationships.

Interpersonal relations differ from social, that is, collective relations by their own characteristics. Emotional feelings form the basis of interpersonal relations, they are formed on the basis of human feelings and emotions, and they are the organizer of people's relations with each other. To describe the concept of interpersonal relations, it is first necessary to refer to its psychological interpretations.

According to A.V.Petrovskiy, M.G.Yaroshevskiy, interpersonal relations are subjective experiences between people, which are reflected objectively in their character. Also, methods of interpersonal relations, cooperative activities are expressed in the influence of people on each other in the process of communication.

E.V.Andrienko also addressed the issue of interpersonal relations in his research. According to him, interpersonal relations are a unique social system, the center of which is manifested by the person himself, his needs, motives, leading individual characteristics, and social aspects.

E.O.Smirnova also approached interpersonal relations in a unique way. According to him, interpersonal relations are the main phenomenon that ensures a person's adaptation to the community, his status, success or failure.

V.V.Abramenko also interpreted interpersonal relations in his own way. According to him, interpersonal relations are manifested as an expression of subjective experiences between children, and represent the content of joint actions and joint activities between them. Interpersonal relations between students, the actions expected of them, embodies the rules, and based on it, it embodies the purpose and content of the joint activity among the student team. Interpersonal relationships take place between students and students, students and students, and students and teachers. The formation and development of interpersonal relations among students is one of the unique components of the organization of the educational process. R. Safarova, F.Aminova, Kh.Nazarova, Z.Kholmatova put forward the opinion that communication is the basis of interpersonal relations. Specialists tried to justify the communication psychologically and pedagogically.

M.S.Lisina tried to theoretically base the relationship between communication and attitude. According to him, mutual relations appear as an integral part of communication. The process of communication is the main means of mutual embodiment of people. That is why communication is a component of personal development. The communication process is the main way to unite people. Accordingly, communication is a component of joint action. That is why interlocutors support each other spiritually. Educators and psychologists have also put forward conflicting opinions about the relationship between communication and interpersonal relationships. According to V.N.Myasishev, communication and relationship have different character functions according to their nature. In her research, N.A.Shkuricheva characterized communication as an independent, unique form of activity.

In most scientific approaches, interpersonal relations were evaluated as a phenomenon that expresses the emotional mood of a group of students. Such studies include Sh.Doniyorov, N.Dilova, F.Muzaffarova, A.A.Bodalev, A.I.Donsov, I.G.Tikhanova, A.N.Lutoshkin. According to experts, joint activity is the main means of creating satisfaction among students.

Activity-based aspects of interpersonal relations are expressed in N.N. Obozova's conceptual approaches. According to his opinion, interpersonal relations are clearly manifested as a means of joint group activity. Interpersonal relationships directly affect the development of each student and group of students.

S.G.Jacobson distinguished two types of interpersonal relationships in his research. They are formed in the process of activity and attitude. Such relations are directed to the formation of joint activities of students step by step. The tasks facing the participants of the joint activity process require individual students to change their behavior in a positive direction. Because their behavior should be convenient for solving tasks that allow joint activities. Otherwise, the behavior of such students prevents joint activities. It is important for students to be able to direct their desires to fulfill the goals and tasks of joint activities. Accordingly, the formation of interpersonal relationships among students is a favorable opportunity for their development, and as a result, it creates a basis for the formation of certain attitudes, beliefs, and valuable directions in students. This helps students to express themselves as individuals by accelerating socialization. This process has the character of regularity and continuity.

In the process of interpersonal relations, students' attitude towards the environment and the people living in it changes. As a result, fundamental changes occur in the educational and developmental activities of students. In the process of interpersonal relations, students develop the ability to reflect, which effectively affects their development. With the help of reflection, students are able to compare their own values, their thoughts with those of their classmates and those around them. Such a comparison is especially characteristic of teenage students. With the help of reflection, students understand the correctness of their actions and for what purpose they were carried out. As a result, students will have the ability to approach themselves from the point of view of others. At the same time, they evaluate their actions and behavior from the point of view of others.

In the process of interpersonal relations, qualities of independence and freedom are formed in students. Today's socio-cultural processes require students to strive for independence, freedom of thought, responsibility for their actions, and the development of executive activities. Independence occurs as a result of the student doing what his own perspective dictates. In the process of interpersonal relations, students become interested in the interests and behavior of their peers. They begin to recognize the qualities of their peers that are acceptable to them. As a result, students develop a sense of individuality, the idea that "I am different", "I am unique", "I am not like anyone else" is strengthened. This is a characteristic characteristic of every person throughout his life and determines the path of his individual development. During this period, the concept of self, i.e. self, is formed and solidified in students. The identity of each student begins to manifest itself in the process of interpersonal relations. As a result, the attitude towards oneself and others is formed. In this way, each student's position in the team, individual point of view begins to appear. As a result, students begin to understand each other. The attitude and assessment of adults towards students affects their relationship to themselves and others to one degree or another. The attitude of students towards their peers and classmates is important in the formation of their attitude towards themselves. As a result, they are able to independently analyze and evaluate their capabilities. Students' sense of self helps determine the nature of their relationships with their peers.

According to psychologists, students tend to express their point of view about everything and events. Such qualities are formed in students as a result of their self-awareness. Students' self-concept and self-evaluation skills are also formed in the process of interpersonal relationships. This, in turn, stabilizes. As a result of self-assessment, students' sense of identity begins to develop in a stable way.

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